

Soil and crop management

Effect of different methods and time of threshing on IR6 grain losses

C. A. Khuhro, I. M. Bhatti, and M. H. Balock, Rice Research Institute, Dokri, Sind, Pakistan

Threshing is a source of substantial postharvest grain losses. Traditional threshing in Sind Province, Pakistan, is by animal trampling after paddy has been stacked for as long as 1-2 mo. This method leads to large grain losses and grain quality deterioration.

We studied the effect of different methods and time of threshing on grain losses at three locations. Hand, bullock, and mechanical threshing were tested at 4 d and 3, 6, and 9 wk after harvest, using grain at the top, middle, and bottom of the stacks (see table).

Analysis of individual threshing methods for different times of stacking in different portions showed that hand threshing and mechanical threshing

Effect of threshing methods and timing on total grain loss, ^a Sind, Pakistan.

Threshing method	Total grain loss ^b (%)					
	Top of stack		Middle of stack		Bottom of stack	
	<i>4 d after harvest</i>					
Hand	0.27	e	0.26	e	0.28	e
Bullock	4.23	de	4.00	de	4.37	de
Mechanical	0.55	e	0.55	de	0.56	e
	<i>3 wk</i>					
Hand	0.34	e	0.43	e	0.44	e
Bullock	5.54	cde	8.2	de	12.87	ab
Mechanical	0.40	e	0.50	e	0.64	e
	<i>6 wk</i>					
Hand	0.32	e	0.56	e	0.50	e
Bullock	4.95	de	4.11	de	13.06	ab
Mechanical	0.72	e	0.66	e	0.58	e
	<i>9 wk</i>					
Hand	0.27	e	0.51	e	0.60	e
Bullock	10.89	ab	4.04	bcd	16.09	a
Mechanical	0.92	e	0.97	e	0.73	e

^a Means of 3 replications at 3 locations. ^b Separation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

produced minimum grain losses. However, with bullock threshing, grain losses increased when threshing was delayed. The bottom portion of the

stack was most seriously affected. Those losses can be minimized to 4% if bullock threshing is not delayed beyond 4 d after harvest. □

Effect of organic and inorganic manuring on rice nurseries

M. S. Maskina, O. P. Meelu, and P. S. Sandhu, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

A combination of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers can improve the root environment and release of nutrients to rice nurseries.

We studied the effect of using a combination of organic and inorganic nitrogen on the rice nursery at PAU farm in 1981 and 1982. Soil was a loamy sand (Ustochrept) with pH 8.4, low organic carbon (0.23%), and 87-8-86 kg available NPK/ha.

N was applied at 0, 60, and 120 kg/ha. Farmyard manure, poultry manure, and azolla were applied at 15, 4, and 10 t/ha. In one treatment, dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata* was raised for 1 mo and incorporated as green manure 3 d before sowing the rice nursery. Dhaincha fresh

weight was 8 to 10 t/ha. Organic manures and 10 kg P/ha were applied before last puddling. Nitrogen was applied in equal splits at sowing and at 15 and 30 d after sowing. Nurseries were in 10- × 2-m² beds and planted with 1 kg seed. Beds were sown the last week of May and data were recorded 45 d later.

Green manure combined with 60 kg N/ha produced nursery plant biomass equal to that with 120 kg N/ha (see table). Height, color, and leaves of nursery plants were affected favorably by the application of green manure and poultry manure. Seedling strength (see table) was determined as dry matter per unit height

$$\left(\frac{\text{dry matter of the plant (mg)}}{\text{ht of the plant (cm)}} \right)$$

and was highest in the green manure treatment.

Uptake of essential macro- and micro-nutrients improved with application of organic manures (see figure). Uptake of

Effect of organic manures on uptake of essential nutrients by nursery plants (mean 1981-82), Ludhiana, India.